

Urban Expansion and Landscape Structure Changes in Kpalimé City (Togo) Between 1985 and 2024: GIS Approach, Landscape Metrics and CA-Markov Modeling

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ABSTRACT

African cities are undergoing significant changes with multiple social, economic, and environmental consequences. This study aims to assess the spatio-temporal changes in land cover in the city of Kpalimé (Togo) between 1985 and 2024, in order to analyze urban expansion, its landscape impacts, and its future prospects. The approach is based on the use of Landsat satellite data (TM, ETM+, OLI/TIRS) from 1985, 2000, 2015, and 2024, downloaded from the Google Earth Engine platform, and on the use of remote sensing indices (NDVI, NDBI, BU), combined with supervised classification (MLC) using ArcGIS 10.4. Four land cover classes were distinguished: Agglomerations, Crops/fallows, bare soil, and forest lands. Eight (8) landscape ecology indicators were calculated, including dominance (pland), aggregation (ai, clumpy), fragmentation and connectivity (np, cohesion), plot morphology (Frac_mn), and diversity (shdi, sisi). The accuracy of the classifications was deemed satisfactory (84.6% to 94%), with Kappa coefficients ranging from 0.79 to 0.92, ensuring the reliability of the results. The analyzes highlight a significant increase in agglomerations, which rose from 429.07 ha (5.13%) in 1985 to 1,624.26 ha (44.11%) in 2024, representing a gain of 1,195.19 ha. This growth was concentrated primarily between 2000 and 2015 (779.84 ha), a period characterized by intense land pressure and uncontrolled urbanization. After a prolonged decline, crops/fallows have recently rebounded (528.28 ha between 2015 and 2024), while forestlands, initially expanding, have experienced a significant decrease (-1106.6 ha between 2015 and 2024) due to human pressures and increasing urbanization. Landscape indicators confirm increased fragmentation of the urban fabric at the turn of the millennium, followed by a process of consolidation and densification, characteristic of evolving urban dynamics. Predictive modeling, carried out using Markov chains (MOLUSCE plugin for QGIS 3.40), projects an expansion of built-up areas to 2119.02 ha (57.58%) by 2050, confirming the trend of accelerated urbanization at the expense of natural and agricultural areas. These results highlight a crucial issue for the urban and environmental planning of Kpalimé. They emphasize the urgent need to develop integrated territorial policies capable of guiding urban growth while preserving the ecological functions and agricultural resources essential to the sustainability and resilience of the city.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Urbanization today represents one of the greatest challenges to the sustainability of socio-ecological systems, particularly in developing countries. Accelerated urbanization thus presents a global challenge with complex socio-ecological dimensions (Acuto et al. 2023). Globally, the urban population continues to grow rapidly, and by 2050, nearly 70% of humanity will live in urban areas, with a high concentration of this growth in Africa and Asia (Chesnay 2023). While this trend can foster economic development, it also generates intense pressure on natural resources, infrastructure, and services, exacerbating social inequalities and environmental vulnerabilities (Africa 2022; UN-DESA 2023).

One of the most visible manifestations of this growth is urban sprawl, that is, the unplanned and often chaotic expansion of cities into their peripheries. This process is generally accompanied by excessive land consumption, habitat fragmentation, the loss of agricultural land, and increased ecological pressures on urban and peri-urban areas (Linard et al. 2013; Liu et al. 2022). In many contexts, it is fueled by inadequate land governance, increasing real estate speculation, and unequal access to basic amenities (Habitat 2020).

Africa is particularly affected by this dynamic. With an urbanization rate reaching 44% in 2022, the continent is experiencing the fastest urban growth in the world (Commission 2022). This uncontrolled urban expansion leads to the proliferation of informal settlements, often built outside of urban planning regulations, and contributes to the degradation of local ecosystems (Africa 2022; UN-DESA 2023; Tejjido-Murias et al. 2024; Belden et al. 2025). The challenge, therefore, is to reconcile urban growth and sustainability through appropriate planning tools.

In Togo, between 2010 and 2022, the population increased by an average of 2.3% per year, with an urbanization rate of 43% (INSEED 2023). Plateaux region, home to more than 20% of the national population, is experiencing rapid and often informal urbanization. In Kpalimé, one of the main urban centers in this region, land use occurs largely outside of regulatory frameworks, with little consideration for environmental issues or existing planning tools.

In this context, the need for sustainable urban planning is paramount. Spatial analysis based on landscape ecology, combined with tools such as geographic information systems (GIS) and predictive models like CA-Markov, makes it possible to anticipate land-use dynamics and assess their consequences (Yadav and Ghosh 2021; He et al. 2023). It is within a framework that the present study is situated, aiming to model the urban sprawl of the city of Kpalimé using geographic information systems (GIS) and the CA-Markov model, in order to identify and assess the spatial and functional transformations of land use in this urban area.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study area

Kpalimé city, located 120 kilometers from the capital Lomé, is the administrative center of the Kloto prefecture and lies within ecological zone IV (Ern 1979). This zone encompasses parts of the Kloto 1, 2, and 3 communes, geographically extending between latitudes 6.86802 and 6.94728 North, and between longitudes 0.561426 and 0.712178 East (Figure 1). Topographically, this city is situated on a plain at an altitude of 200 meters. The mountainous areas are generally located at 370 m, with a maximum slope of 31.34° and are found on Atakora mountain range to the north of the city (Figure 2). Soils are primarily silty, clayey, and sandy. Other than the city's hydrographic network is composed of rivers and streams such as Hé, Agbassandjinou, Kpegolo, Hétoè, Bla and Adedze.

Figure 1: Study area (ZUK)

Figure 2: ZUK relief

From a climatic point of view, Kpalimé benefits from a transitional Guinean sub-equatorial climate, characterized by a bimodal regime. A substantial rainy season extends from mid-March to October, interspersed with a short dry season

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from mid-July to mid-August, characterized by a decrease in rainfall, followed by a longer period of the main dry season from November to mid-March. Kpalimé ranks among the wettest urban centers in the country, with rainfall reaching 1900 mm per year, while average annual temperatures are around 22°C (Adamou 2008).

The region's plant ecosystem exhibits a diversity ranging from Sudanese-Guinean type mountain forest to wooded savannah in the plains, enhanced by gallery forests along bodies of water.

The population of the city of Kpalimé is composed of diverse socio-cultural groups unevenly distributed across the territory. The indigenous population is the Ewe, and the non-indigenous population comprises various ethnic groups such as the Kabye, Kotokoli, Moba, Lamba, Nawda, and Hausa. According to the latest census, this population is estimated at 87,478 inhabitants including 42,058 men and 45,420 women (INSEED 2023). The inhabitants of the region engage in various economic activities, including trade, crafts, raising small ruminants and poultry, as well as agriculture (such as cereals, legumes and tubers, as well as cash crops like coffee, cocoa, avocado and cola).

B. Data Collection and Processing

B-1) Satellite images

Table 1: Characteristics of satellite images

No.	Sensors	Dates
1	TM	12/03/1985
2	ETM+	08/04/2000
3	OLI TIRS	10/04/2015
4	OLI TIRS	15/05/2024

Note: Resolution 30m

Table 2: Sensor Characteristics

Satellites	Sensors	Spatial resolution
Landsat 5	TM (Thematic Mapper)	30 m (bands 1-5, 7), 120 m (thermal band 6)
Landsat 7	ETM+ (Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus)	30 m (bands 1-5, 7), 60 m (thermal band 6), 15 m (panchromatic band 8)
Landsat 8	OLI (Operational Land Imager), TIRS (Thermal Infrared Sensor)	30 m (multi-spectral bands 1-7, 9), 15 m (panchromatic band 8), 100 m (thermal bands 10-11)
Landsat 8 & 9	OLI-2 (Landsat 9), TIRS-2 (Landsat 9), OLI/TIRS (Landsat 8)	multispectral bands 1-7, 9), 15 m (panchromatic band 8), 100 m (thermal bands 10-11)

The study was conducted using high-resolution Landsat 5, 7, 8, and 9 satellite images from 1985, 2000, 2015, and 2024 (Table 1). These images were downloaded free of charge from the Google Earth Engine platform

(<https://uc.appengine.google.com>) and included several spectral bands with different characteristics (Table 2). The images underwent preprocessing to minimize atmospheric cover, making them effective for quantifying land-use changes and calculating metrics (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Architecture of the method used

B-2) City expansion rate

To calculate the annual rate of urban expansion, the following formula is used:

$$V = \frac{S_2 - S_1}{t_2 - t_1}$$

As for the calculation of the average annual rate of urban expansion (in %), this formula for the geometric growth rate is used:

$$TCAM (CAGR) = \left(\left(\frac{S_2}{S_1} \right)^{\frac{1}{t_2 - t_1}} - 1 \right) * 100$$

with: S_1 and S_2 , the urban areas (in ha) at two dates; $t_2 - t_1$ being the time interval (in years); V is the annual rate of expansion (ha/year) and CAGR, the growth rate (in %).

As for Pearson's coefficient, it is calculated using the following formula:

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})(Y_i - \bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \bar{Y})^2}}, \quad \text{where: } r \text{ is}$$

Pearson's linear correlation coefficient; X_i and Y_i are the values of the two variables studied; \bar{X} and \bar{Y}_n is the means

of these variables.

B-3) Remote sensing indices

Table 3: Characteristics of urban indices

Clues	Formulas	Interpretations
NDVI	$NDVI = \frac{NIR-Red}{NIR+Red}$	<0: Water ≈0: Bare soil 0, 2–1: Vegetation
	• Landsat 5 (TM) $NDVI = \frac{Band4-Band3}{Band4+Band3}$	
	• Landsat 7 (ETM+) $NDVI = \frac{Band4-Band3}{Band4+Band3}$	
	• Landsat 8 and 9 (OLI/TIRS) $NDVI = \frac{Band5-Band4}{Band5+Band4}$	
NDBI	$NDBI = \frac{SWIR-NIR}{SWIR+NIR}$	>0: Built-up areas <0: Vegetation
	• Landsat 5 (TM) $NDBI = \frac{Band5-Band4}{Band5+Band4}$	
	• Landsat 7 (ETM+) $NDBI = \frac{Band5-Band4}{Band5+Band4}$	
	• Landsat 8 and 9 (OLI) $NDBI = \frac{Band6-Band5}{Band6+Band5}$	
BU	$BU = NDBI - NDVI$	>0: Urban <0: Non-urban

Three (3) calculations urban indices were chosen (Zha et al. 2003) of which The NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) for vegetation in an area, the NDBI (Normalized Difference Building Index) for built-up areas, and the BU (Table 3) are used. This adjusted method allows the calculation of the BU index for different images, where a higher pixel value reflects a greater probability that it represents a built-up area.

- NDVI Index (Fousseni et al., 2011; Rouse Jr et al., 1974) uses near-infrared (NIR) and visible red (Red) to identify built-up areas, agricultural land and vegetation cover density with values ranging from -1 to +1. Negative values correspond to water surfaces; close to 0 for bare land and can reach +1 for vegetation areas.

- NDBI index is based on the spectral characteristics of built-up areas and vegetation cover. This index is used to extract built-up areas from remote sensing images and is calculated using the mid-infrared (SWIR) and near-infrared (NIR) wavelengths, generating values between -1 and +1. (Zha et al. 2003).

- BU Index is a transformation that uses the short-wave infrared (SWIR) and near-infrared bands to better distinguish urban areas from vegetated areas. Positive values generally indicate built-up areas, while negative values correspond to vegetation or other surfaces. Values range from -∞ to +∞. (Rouse Jr et al. 1974; Tucker 1979; Cavalli et al. 2008; Chander et al. 2009)

B-4) Classification of the land use (land cover)

A multitude of land classifications are used at the global or local level. The one adopted in the urban context is recorded in Table 4.

Table 4: Typology of occupation classes selected

No	Level 1	Level 2
1	Built areas	Residential areas (housing, buildings, housing estates)
		Commercial and industrial (shops, factories, offices)
		Infrastructure (roads, schools, hospitals, etc.)
		Bare ground
2	Non-areas built	Bodies of water
		Mosaic of crops/fallow land
		Forest lands
		Savannas

Composite images from the various selected years were imported into ArcGIS 10.4 software, and then, through supervised classification, the Maximum Likelihood Classification (MLC) was used. East an approach probabilistic, which uses sampling areas to determine the classes of each cell (or pixel) in an image. Indeed, this distribution Statistical analysis using both variance and covariance of the class signature derived from the different formations during the assignment of each pixel produces the lowest probability of classification errors (Mohia 2018).

B-5) Classification evaluation methods

Good accuracy in land cover classification need several methods such as including the overall

accuracy and Cohen's Kappa coefficient. These measurements are obtained from the confusion matrix which compares the classes obtained by automatic classification with reference points whose characteristics are known (El Garouani and Aharik 2021). Overall classification accuracy is a metric used to evaluate the performance of a classification model. It represents the percentage of observations correctly classified by the model relative to the total number of observations. To ensure the representativeness of this index and to limit imperfections, the accuracy of each class taken separately was calculated.

$$\text{Overall accuracy} = \frac{\text{Total number of correct samples}}{\text{Total number of samples}} *$$

100

Kappa coefficient (K), introduced by Jacob Cohen, is a statistical measure used to assess the agreement between two evaluators or classification methods, taking into account the agreement due to chance. Widely used in remote sensing, this

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coefficient indicates how well the data to be classified agree with the reference data and constitutes a reliable measure in the evaluation of thematic classifications by examining all elements of the confusion matrix, and takes into account both errors of omission and commission (Landis and Koch 1977). It is calculated as follows:

$$K = \frac{Tp * (Tp \text{ classify}) - \sum(Tl * Tc)}{Tp^2 - \sum(Tl * Tc)}$$

Tp: Total pixels; Tl: Total rows; Tc: Total columns

The tables below allow for the interpretation of the overall accuracy and the Kappa coefficient respectively.

Table 5: Reference values for interpreting overall accuracy and Kappa values

Overall accuracy values	Interpretations	Kappa coefficient values	Interpretations
< 50%	Insufficient	< 0	Bad
50-70%	Poor	0 to 0.2	Negligible
70-80%	Acceptable	0.41 to 0.6	Weak
80-90%	Good	0.61 to 0.8	Good
> 90%	Very good	0.81 to 1	Excellent

Source: (Kohavi and John

1998) Source: (Cohen 1960; Landis and Koch 1977)
ArcGIS 10.4 software was used to calculate the confusion matrix, where 150 random points, based on the different classes, were generated for each year to assess the accuracy. For thorough validation of the classes, a combined method using Google Earth Pro software and field visits to the study area was adopted.

B-6) Landscape metrics

Table 6: Description of selected landscape metrics

Metrics	Acronyms	Types	Descriptions and interpretations
Aggregation index	ai	Aggregation metric	Spots of the same type are aggregated to this degree. A high index indicates a high aggregation of spots of the same type. The closer the index is to 100, the more aggregated the tasks are. Its unit is the percentage (%).
Clumpy index	clumpy	Aggregation metric	Spots of the same type are grouped together to this degree. A high index indicates a strong tendency for spots to form groups. The closer the index is to 1, the more clustered the spots are. It is dimensionless (value between -1 and 1).
Cohesion index	cohesion	Aggregation metric	It is the degree of physical connectivity of tasks of the

			same type. A high index indicates strong physical connectivity of tasks of the same type. The closer the index is to 100, the more connected the tasks are. The unit of this index is the percentage (%).
Fractal dimension index	frac_mn	shape metric	It represents the complexity of spot shapes based on perimeter-area relationships. A high index indicates increased complexity of spot shapes. The closer the index is to 2, the more complex the spot shapes. Unitless (value between 1 and 2)
Number of patches	np	Aggregation metric	This is the total number of spots in the landscape. A large number of patches indicates a high level of landscape fragmentation. The higher the number, the more fragmented the landscape. This index is expressed as a number.
Proportion of the landscape	Pland	Surface and border metric	This index represents the proportion of the landscape occupied by a specific type of patch. A high value indicates extensive landscape coverage by that type of patch. The unit is percentage (%).
Shannon Diversity Index	shdi	Diversity metric	This is a measure of landscape diversity based on the types of patches. A high index indicates a wide diversity of spot types. The higher the index, the greater the diversity of spot types. Unitless (positive value)
Simpson's Diversity Index	sidi	Diversity metric	A measure of landscape dominance based on the types of patches. High index indicates a low dominance of one or a few types of tasks. The closer the index is to 1, the higher the diversity. Unitless (value between 0 and 1)

Source: (Hesselbarth et al. 2019; McGarigal et al. 2023)

Following classification and remote sensing analysis, landscape measurements were calculated for each of the 1985, 2000, 2015, and 2024 maps. Table 6 below shows the different metrics selected. Eight (8) landscape metrics were determined using an R package called ' *landscapemetrics* ' (Hesselbarth et al. 2019) derived from the FRAGSTATS software (McGarigal et al. 2023). Some of these metrics describe the characteristics of the different classes, while others describe the landscapes themselves. For example, the aggregation index (*ai*), the clustering index (*clumpy*), the task cohesion index (*cohesion*), and the number of tasks (*np*)

were chosen to measure the aggregation of urban entities. As for the metrics related to shape, area, and edge; these are the following metrics: fractal dimension indices (*Frac_mn*) and landscape proportion (*pland*). To assess the diversity of the urban area, two (02) metrics were used : the Shannon diversity index (*shdi*) and the Simpson diversity index (*sidi*).

B-7) Future prediction model

To anticipate changes in land use in the study area (ZUK), an approach combining Markov chain modeling and geographic information systems (GIS) was adopted. (Essid 2012). This is a methodology based on probabilistic and spatial principles, thus allowing the simulation of land cover dynamics in a reliable and consistent manner (Figure 4).

In geomatics, two main categories of predictive models are generally used: deterministic models and stochastic models. (Ladet et al. 2005). The former rely on physical or empirical laws assumed time-invariant, while the latter adopt a probabilistic approach, including Markov chains. These model the transitions from one state to another based on probabilities deduced from previous states (Delmas et al. 2019). Introduced at the beginning of the 20th by Russian mathematician Andrei Markov, they allow us to represent changes of state in complex systems, such as land cover dynamics.

In this study, the MOLUSCE (Modules for Land Use Change Evaluation) plugin for QGIS 3.40 was used to leverage the capabilities of spatialized Markov chains through a simulation module developed specifically for this purpose (Muhammad et al. 2022; Amgoth et al. 2023). This extension allows for the analysis of past changes, the modeling of transition potential, and the simulation of future changes. The simulation process involves several steps: input data, change analysis, transition potential modeling, simulation, and validation. These simulations provide a robust framework for decision support in land-use planning and urban spatial management.

Figure 4: Method adopted for prediction model

III. RESULTS

A. City expansion rate

Table 7: Temporal evolution of urban area and population

Years	1985	2000	2015	2024
Areas (Ha)	429.07	562.03	1341.87	1624.26
Populations (inhabitants)	45853	48769	83982	91502

Periods	Initial (S _i)	Final (S _f)	Annual growth rates (ha/year)	CAGR (%/year)
1985–2000	429.07	562.03	8.87	1.89
2000–2015	562.03	1341.87	52	5.86
2015–2024	1341.87	1624.26	31.36	2.13
1985–2024	429.07	1624.26	30.61	3.40

Data above (Table 7) show a marked and simultaneous increase in urban area and population between 1985 and 2024. The urban area nearly quadrupled (from 429 ha to 1624 ha), while the population roughly doubled (from 45,853 to 91,502 inhabitants). Furthermore, the most rapid growth in area occurred between 2000 and 2015, a period during which the area increased by nearly 140%. Between 2015 and 2024, expansion continued, but at a more moderate pace.

Based on Pearson's coefficient ($r = 0.9967$), the evolution of urban area is strongly dependent on the evolution of population according to the equation: $Population = (40.2207 * Area) + 27735.8574$ (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Correlation between area and population

Between 1985 and 2000, urban growth remained relatively moderate, with an average expansion rate of approximately 8.87 hectares per year and an annual growth rate of 1.89%. However, between 2000 and 2015, a clear break in this trend is observed, with an expansion rate reaching 52 hectares per year and an average annual growth rate of 5.86%. This period represents the most dynamic phase of all the timeframes, during which the urban footprint increased dramatically. Between 2015 and 2024, urban growth remains positive but

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is at a slower pace where the rate of expansion is estimated at 31.36 ha per year and the CAGR at 2.13%.

Overall, over the period from 1985 to 2024, the urban area has increased almost fourfold, with an average annual speed of 30.61 ha/year and an average growth rate of 3.40% per year.

B. Urban remote sensing indices

Table 8: Comparative table of indices from 1985 to 2024

Years		1985	2000	2015	2024
NDVI	Min	0.08	0.06	0.08	0.07
	Max	0.38	0.34	0.42	0.40
NDBI	Min	-0.21	-0.17	-0.22	-0.2
	Max	0.11	0.19	0.12	0.18
BU	Min	-0.59	-0.5	-0.55	-0.6
	Max	-0.01	0.11	0.05	0.07

Combined evolution of the NDVI, NDBI, and BU indices highlights the dynamics of vegetation and urbanization in the study area between 1985 and 2024. NDVI values, ranging from 0.06 to 0.08 for the minimums and from 0.34 to 0.42 for the maximums, indicate a generally stable vegetation cover over time (Table 8). Furthermore, the NDBI and BU indices show that their minimum values decreased from -0.22 to -0.17 and from -0.60 to -0.50, respectively, while their maximum values increased from 0.11 to 0.19 and from -0.01 to 0.11. The correlation coefficient calculated between the mean NDVI and the mean BU is $r = -0.6323$ (Figure 6)

Figure 6: Correlation between NDVI and BU indices

NDBI shows a more contrasting trend. Maximum values decreased from 1985 to 2015 (from 0.267 to 0.107). However, the rebound to 0.189 in 2024 indicates a renewed urbanization dynamic (Figure 7). Finally, the BU index clearly reveals increasing urbanization over the decades. Maximum values, very low in 1985 (0.008), have steadily increased to reach 0.027 in 2024. Minimum values, on the other hand, fluctuate considerably, reaching a low in 2000 (-0.651) and remaining very negative in 2024 (-0.612).

Figure 7: Urban indices evolution

C. Multi-temporal variation of different occupation classes

Series of thematic maps, representing land use in the urban area of Kpalimé in 1985, 2000, 2015, and 2024, provides an overview of the major landscape transformations the city has undergone. These maps allow us to track the evolution of the human footprint and the state of natural ecosystems over time. Categorization shows a subdivision into four (4) distinct classes (Figure 8): Agglomerations (A), Crops/Fallows (CF), Bare Soil (BS), and Forest Lands (FL).

Figure 8: Dynamics of land cover categories

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In 1985, the A (429.07 ha) and CF (330.46 ha) zones dominated the urban area, totaling 759.53 ha, or more than 84% of the total area (903.01 ha). BS (105.03 ha) and FL (38.45 ha) lands occupied a secondary position, with a combined area of 143.48 ha. Then, in 2000, the CF (42.63%) and A (34.15%) lands remained predominant, totaling nearly 77% of the area, but with a rebalancing between these two classes. FL (11.50%) saw a dramatic increase, rising from 4.26% to 11.50%, while BS (11.72%) remained stable in proportion. As for 2015, A (1341.87 ha) lands dominated the landscape, representing nearly 50% of the total area (2691.67 ha), while CF (974.37 ha) occupied 36.2% of land use. Together, these two classes totaled 2,316.24 ha, representing over 86% of the urban area. FL (252.30 ha) and BS (123.13 ha) categories occupied a secondary position, with a combined area of 375.43 ha. Finally, for the year 2024, the CF (40.80%) and A (44.11%) categories share the territory almost equally, representing over 84% of the total area. FL (7.35%) and BS (7.74%) occupy a secondary place, but BS have rebounded slightly compared to 2015 (Figure 9).

Table 9: Variation in different land use classes

Classes	1985-2000	2000-2015	2015-2024
Agglomerations	132.96	779.84	282.39
Crops/Fallows	371.08	272.83	528.28
Bare soils	87.82	-69.72	161.8
Forest lands	150.87	62.98	18.47

Table 9 highlights the evolution of the main land cover classes between 1985 and 2024, with variations according to the periods. Between 1985 and 2000, BS increased from 105.03 ha (11.63%) to 192.85 ha (11.72%), FL from 38.45 ha (4.26%) to 189.32 ha (11.50%), A from 429.07 ha (47.52%) to 562.03 ha (34.15%) and CF from 330.46 ha (36.59%) to 701.54 ha (42.63%). Between 2000 and 2015, BS decreased to 123.13 ha (4.57%), while FL, A, and CF increased respectively to 252.3 ha (9.37%), 1341.87 ha (49.85%), and 974.37 ha (36.21%). Between 2015 and 2024, all land cover classes increased. The most significant increases were in A at 1624.26 ha (44.11%) and CJ at 1502.65 ha (40.80%).

However, the period 2015-2024 is marked by a significant decline in forests, resulting in a decrease in areas of a rate of 9.67%.

Figure 9: Land use changes analysis between 1985 and 2025

D. Classification assessment

Accuracy of the different classified land cover images was assessed using the confusion matrix. The classification accuracy values recorded for the years 1985, 2000, 2015, and 2024 were 94.03%, 84.62%, 93.5%, and 90.2%, respectively (Table 10). The kappa coefficient values were 0.9152, 0.789, 0.9060, and 0.86, respectively.

Table 10: Confusion matrices and Kappa indices of landuse Classes

1985	A	CF	BS	FL	TI	Tc	Kp
A	9.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	10.0	0,900	0.0000
CF	0.00	20.00	0.00	2.00	22.0	0.909	0.0000
BS	1.00	0.00	9.00	0.000	10.0	0,900	0.0000
FL	0.00	0.00	0.00	25.00	25.0	1,000	0.0000
Tc	10.00	21.00	9.00	27.00	67.0	0.000	0.0000
Pr	0.90	0.952	1.00	0.923	0.0	0.940	0.0000
Kp	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.000	0.9152

2000	A	CF	BS	FL	TI	Tc	Kp
A	10.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	10	1,000	0.000
CF	0.000	17.00	3,000	3,000	23	0.739	0.000
BS	0.000	0.000	10.00	0.000	10	1,000	0.000
FL	1,000	1,000	2,000	18.00	22	0.818	0.000
Tc	11.00	18.00	15.00	21.00	65	0.000	0.000
Pr	0.909	0.944	0.667	0.857	0	0.846	0.000
Kp	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0	0.000	0.789

2015	A	CF	BS	FL	TI	Tc	Kp
A	10,000	0.000	0.000	0	10	1,000	0.000
CF	1,000	10,000	1,000	0	12	0.833	0.000
BS	0.000	0.000	10.00	0	10	1,000	0.000
FL	0.000	2,000	0.000	28	30	0.933	0.000
Tc	11,000	12,000	11.00	28	62	0.000	0.000
Pr	0.909	0.833	0.909	1	0	0.935	0.000
Kp	0.000	0.000	0.000	0	0	0.000	0.906

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2024	A	CF	BS	FL	TI	Tc	Kp
A	9,000	1,000	0	0.000	10	0,900	0.000
CF	1,000	14,000	0	1,000	16	0.875	0.000
BS	1,000	1,000	8	0.000	10	0,800	0.000
FL	0.000	1,000	0	24,000	25	0,960	0.000
Tc	11,00	17,00	8	25,00	61	0.000	0.000
Pr	0.818	0.824	1	0.960	0	0,902	0.000
Kp	0.000	0.000	0	0.000	0.000	0.000	0,861

Note: A = Agglomerations, CF = Crops/fallows, BS = Bare soils, FL = Forest lands,

TI = Total rows, Tc = Total columns, Pu = User precision, Pr = Producer precision and Kp = Kappa.

E. Landscape metrics

E-1) Dominance index (Pland)

This metric expresses the relative share (in %) occupied by each land class in the landscape. In 1985, A (52.48%) followed by CF (37.36%) occupied the majority of the land, while FL (4.03%) had the smallest area. In 2000, this distribution was different, with CF dominating (45.56%), a slight increase compared to 1985. From 2000 to 2024, after a gradual increase in A (from 41.45% to 51.64%), there was a decrease in FL, from 10.15% to 5.3%. Opposite trend was observed for A at the CF level (45.46% in 2000; 32.34% in 2015; then 41.49% in 2024). Bare soils remain a small part of the study area (Figure 11). In a second phase, with the increase in A, there were various anthropogenic pressures on FL, thus creating an increase in CF.

Figure 10: Dominance indice evolution

E-2) Fragmentation and connectivity indices (Cohesion and np)

To analyze fragmentation and connectivity of the ZUK, two indices were calculated: cohesion, which represents the overall connectivity of fragments or patches within a landscape, and the number of patches (np), indicating the set of distinct spatial units that make up each land use class. Thus, in 1985 and 2000, A (98.06%; 95.76%) and CF (90.28%; 90.54%) classes exhibited strong cohesion (Figure 12); FL (76.18%) were the least connected. During these

same periods, the CF (33 and 89 respectively) were the most fragmented, while FL (10 and 38) represented the least fragmented. Then, for the years 2015 and 2024, we observe a densification of the A areas with a cohesion of approximately 98.70% and 98.65%, respectively. In contrast to urban areas, the cohesion of the BS areas decreases sharply (35.47% and 48.05%). Finally, over the same period, the np index of the A and CF increases (from 45, 62 to 106 and 142).

Figure 11: Fragmentation and connectivity indices evolution

E-3) Spatial aggregation index (ai and «clumpy»)

Aggregation index (ai) measures the tendency of fragments to clump together or disperse within the landscape, while the «clumpy» index measures the spatial agglomeration of fragments, taking into account their proximity. In 1985, A were characterized by very high indices (89.49%) and (0.78) for ai and «clumpy» respectively. Furthermore, FL (65.31%) for ai and CF (0.59) for the second index showed a more pronounced dispersion (Figure 13).

A slight decrease in the ai index occurred in 2000 (from 89.49% to 80.23%) and in «clumpy» index (from 0.78 to 0.66) for A. CF and FL remained aggregated (68.59% and 60.27%, respectively). An expansionary phenomenon was then observed with a strong ai index for A (84.27% and 82.52%) in the period 2015-2024. Similarly, FL maintained a high level of aggregation (0.52 and 0.50 for the «clumpy»

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index), albeit slightly increasing, while BS remained the most dispersed (0.29 and 0.40).

Figure 12: Evolution of aggregation indices

E-4) Fragment morphology index (Frac_mn)

It represents the complexity or shape of the fragments. Thus, values close to 1 indicate simple shapes, and complex shapes have values close to 2. In general, all classes exhibit high values (1.014 to 1.060). There was also a slight increase in the complexity of A in 1985 (1.020), 2000 (1.032), and 2015 (1.033), followed by a stabilization close to 1.039 in 2024 (Figure 14). The highest value was obtained in the CF in 1985. The other classes also showed very little variation.

Figure 13: Fragment morphology indice evolution

E-5) Diversity indices (shdi and sidi)

The Shannon diversity index (shdi) measures the richness and balance in the distribution of land cover classes, reflecting both the number of cover types present and the homogeneity of their distribution, while the Simpson index (sidi) gives more weight to the dominant classes in the landscape distribution. In 1985, the shdi index was very high (1.007). This diversity then decreased slightly to 0.93 in 2024 (Figure 13). A similar trend was observed for the sidi index , although it remained somewhat lower. This index reveals that initially some classes were more prevalent than others, but this dominance has diminished over time, decreasing from 0.579 in 1985 to 0.558 in 2024.

Figure 14: Evolution of diversity indices

F. Future prediction of the ZUK urban landscape

F-1) Validation of the transition model

This model's learning curve shows a steady decrease in error during training, resulting in a very low final value (0.008). In parallel, cross-validation reveals a high Kappa index of 0.95 (Figure 16a). The additional figure (Figure 16b), showing a Kappa index of 0.99, further confirms this accuracy in the prediction.

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Figure 15: Characteristics of the transition and validation model

Analysis of the figure reveals several land cover transitions between 2000 and 2024. Three (3) major changes are observed: a major shift in land cover budget classes such as CF and FL to A and FL to CF; a moderate maintenance of some classes from 2000 (A and FL); and a minor shift in all classes. The most significant change is the conversion of FL and CF to A.

Figure 16: Different changes in occupation classes between 2000 and 2024

F-2) Land use projections for 2050

Projection (Figures 18 and 19) shows a significant change in land cover in the ZUK by 2050. A are projected to expand by 494.76 ha, increasing its share from 1624.26 ha (44.11%) to 2119.02 ha (57.58%) of the territory. Conversely, CF are projected to decrease from 1502.65 ha (40.98%) to 1137.39 ha (30.90%). At the same time, FL is expected to increase slightly by 62.92 ha. BS, on the other hand are projected to decrease significantly (from 7.22% to 2.45%).

Figure 17: 2050 prediction based on the CA-Markov model

Figure 18: Evolution of occupation classes according to the prediction

IV. DISCUSSIONS

A. Spatio-temporal analysis of urban expansion using remote sensing

Between 1985 and 2024, Kpalimé urban area underwent a profound spatial transformation, characteristic of urban trajectories observed in many African cities. Over the entire period, the urban area nearly quadrupled, while the population only doubled, reflecting marked urban sprawl with low density. Although population growth and spatial expansion are strongly correlated ($r = 0.9967$), this relationship masks complex structural dynamics. According to Kwasi Gyau Baffour Awuah (2022), this trend is explained by increased land speculation, weak regulation of real estate markets, and a political preference for expansion rather than densification. Folega et al. (2023) emphasize that urban sprawl leads to the loss of agricultural land and the fragmentation of natural ecosystems. Furthermore, this dynamic is exacerbated by increasing informal urbanization marked by similar socio-spatial imbalances, with peripheries often lacking basic infrastructure (Cheriguene 2024).

Three major periods have been identified, including moderate urbanization and relative ecological resilience (1985 to 2000), then the brutal acceleration of urbanization

and territorial recomposition (2000 to 2015) and finally the densification of the remaining urban spaces (2015–2024).

The first phase is characterized by slow and gradual urban growth, with an average expansion rate estimated at 8.87 ha/year. This reflects urbanization still limited by economic constraints following a future structural adjustment (Bawa 2017). Bah (2023) argues that this phase corresponds to a slow transition, where African cities struggle to absorb migration flows due to reduced public investment capacity. In terms of land use, the territory remains predominantly dominated by crops or fallow land, while bare soil and artificial surfaces remain marginal. Concurrently, a notable increase in forest land is observed, suggesting either a temporary reduction in human pressures or the effect of reforestation or natural regeneration programs, as reported in other West African contexts (Gueye et al. 2024). Remote sensing data confirm this relative environmental stability. Indeed, the stability of the maximum NDVI observed in this study, despite urban expansion, is echoed in the work of Eloma Ikoleki et al. (2025), who demonstrate that protection strategies and favorable rainfall patterns allow for the maintenance, or even the increase, of vegetation density in contexts of intense urbanization. Their results, based on remote sensing time series, show that areas protected from bushfires exhibit an increase in NDVI of 12 to 18% over 20 years, compared to only 3 to 5% in unprotected areas. Thus, the stability of the maximum NDVI observed in this study, attributable to active conservation measures, reflects a still spatially contained urbanization that has not profoundly altered local ecological balances.

Conversely, the second period marks a sharp break characterized by a rate of expansion reaching 52 ha/year (5.86% per year) with the advent of informal settlements, often at the expense of wetlands or agricultural areas. This can be explained by several factors, including economic liberalization (Imam & Salinas, 2015) and the rise of the urban middle class. (Mercer 2024) and increasingly motorization promoting suburbanization (Tossoukpe et al. 2025). Dibba et al. (2025) and Opong et al. (2025) observe similar trends in certain West African countries, notably Gambia and Ghana (Accra), where rapid urbanization has led to coastal degradation. The evolution of land artificialization indicators (NDBI, BU) confirms a continuous progression of urbanization, with distinct phases reflecting underlying socio-economic dynamics. The maximum values of NDBI and BU increase significantly, a trend that Ji et al. (2023) attribute to a phase of accelerated economic growth, marked by massive infrastructure investments and the liberalization of land markets. Their analyses show that during this period, the studied urban area experiences a 40% to 60% increase in artificialized land, with NDBI peaks rising from 0.15 to 0.35 in less than 15 years. In this study, the temporary decrease in the maximum NDBI between 1985 and 2015 (from 0.267 to 0.107) could be explained by local

economic constraints (financial crises, slowdown in investment). Regarding land use, there is a growing dominance of agricultural areas (49.85%) at the expense of crops and fallow land (36.21%) and a drastic reduction in bare soil (4.57%). This trend reflects massive agricultural intensification to meet ever-increasing food demand, a phenomenon extensively documented by Pinheiro & Govind (2020). The relative stabilization of forest areas (9.37%) during this period could be explained by protection measures or the saturation of available space, as observed Gobinath et al. (2024). However, this apparent stability masks underlying pressures, including illegal charcoal production and excessive logging, which continue to threaten forest ecosystems (Gueye et al. 2024).

Finally, the last period is characterized by a relative slowdown in urban expansion (31.36 ha/year) resulting from the saturation of available space, a growing awareness of the limits of urban sprawl (Bhatia et al. 2024), and the rugged terrain of the urban area (Shi et al. 2023). This spatial acceleration is accompanied by a marked restructuring of land cover classes. Indeed, cultivated and fallow land is expanding significantly, while bare soil is decreasing, reflecting agricultural intensification aimed at meeting increasing food demand (Pinheiro and Govind 2020). At the same time, forest areas are stagnating, or even beginning to decline, revealing increased pressures related to urban expansion and the energy uses of wood (Bimare and Atakpama 2022).

Remote sensing indices confirm these contrasting dynamics. While artificialization indices continue to increase, reflecting a progressive densification of built-up areas (Sondou et al. 2024; Mutua 2025), the maximum NDVI remains relatively stable. This stability reflects the existence of ecological resilience mechanisms linked to the protection of certain areas (parks, floodplains, slopes) and local conservation policies (Guechi et al. 2022). Nevertheless, the persistent negative correlation between NDVI and BU indicates that this resilience remains localized and insufficient to compensate for the overall loss of vegetation cover.

Over the entire study period, the trajectory of the Kpalimé urban area illustrates a model of extensive urbanization. Indeed, the near-perfect correlation between population growth and spatial expansion ($r = 0.9967$) should not obscure the underlying challenges. This urbanization model, based on a linear equation ($\text{Population} = 40.2207 \times \text{Area} + 27735.8574$), generates low density and suboptimal infrastructure, with direct consequences for the climate resilience of cities (Deton et al. 2025). Furthermore, there is a warning about the increased risks of flooding and water stress in urban peripheries (Borah 2025), where soil sealing and the lack of sanitation networks exacerbate the vulnerability of populations. These challenges are particularly acute in Lomé, where recurring floods in outlying neighborhoods (Takili et

al. 2022) illustrate the limitations of unplanned urbanization. These findings confirm the urban transition models described in recent literature, where rapid urban expansion is accompanied by a profound transformation of agricultural and natural spaces (UN-Habitat, 2020; Tudor, C., & Sova, 2021; Oladokoun et al., 2024). They underscore the need to adopt integrated and resilient urban policies that combine land regulation, controlled densification, protection of natural spaces, and the integration of ecosystem services into territorial planning (Artmann et al. 2019; Zeng et al. 2022; Mell 2022).

B. Classification assessment

Accuracy of the various classified land cover images was assessed using the confusion matrix. The classification accuracy values recorded for the different years reveal a generally very satisfactory performance, although fluctuations and challenges specific to certain classes are observable. Kappa coefficient values demonstrate the stability and robustness of the classification model. These results align with those reported by N'guessan Akoguhé et al. (2022); who, in a comprehensive analysis of urban satellite imagery, obtained classification accuracies ranging from 80% to 95% depending on the temporal and spatial resolution of the data. Furthermore, Kabanyegeye (2024) states that the most frequent confusions concern ecologically similar classes (agricultural areas and natural surfaces, as well as transitions between built-up areas and bare soil) in the urban periphery, ambiguities that reflect the spatial complexity of periurban environments. The importance of confusion matrices and kappa coefficient analysis as assessment tools is highlighted by some researchers (Thapa and Murayama 2009; Xing and Meng 2020), who also recommend systematic field validation to limit biases related to automatic classifications, particularly in fragmented and rapidly changing urban landscapes (Tossoukpe et al. 2025).

C. Landscape metrics

Analysis of landscape metrics from this study period reveals major structural transformations in the spatial organization of the territory, marked by contrasting dynamics between land cover classes and a complex evolution of fragmentation, connectivity, and diversity indices. In 1985, the landscape was dominated by agricultural areas, followed by cultivated land and fallow land, while forest formations occupied a marginal space. This initial configuration, similar to that observed by Oladokoun et al. (2024) in Togolese communes (Kozah 1 and 2 then Ogou 1), reflects a traditional agro-landscape structure where extensive agriculture predominates. However, contrary to the trends of continuous forest degradation documented in these works (attributed to intense anthropogenic pressure), our study shows a slight initial expansion of forest lands in the early 2000s, possibly linked to local conservation initiatives, as suggested by (Kombate et al. 2022).

Period from 2000 to 2024 marks a radical transformation of the landscape, with a progressive expansion of agricultural areas at the expense of forest cover, which has decreased significantly. Crops and fallow land, acting as a buffer, fluctuate in importance before regaining ground at the end of the period. This dynamic corroborates the agroforestry transition models described by Dechaicha & Alkama (2020) in Algeria, where agroforestry systems emerge as an intermediate phase before agricultural or urban intensification. BS, marginal throughout the period, confirm their status as landscape remnants, as observed by (Aguejdad and Hubert-Moy 2016) in Rennes (France).

Analysis of fragmentation and connectivity indices reveals divergent trends across land classes. Initially, CF exhibits strong spatial cohesion, while FL, being less connected, form residual pockets. After 2015, a densification of A areas and an increase in their fragmentation are observed, reflecting a spatial restructuring where urbanization first leads to dispersion, then to consolidation. This dynamic, similar to that described by Y. Liu et al. (2025) illustrate a fragmentation-aggregation process typical of landscapes in transition. Spatial aggregation indices confirm this recomposition: CF, initially compact, undergoes a phase of dispersion linked to urban sprawl before reconsolidating, while FL retain a degree of aggregation and BS remain dispersed. These results are consistent with those of (Downes et al. 2024), who demonstrate a progressive densification of urban areas after a sprawl phase.

Analysis of morphological complexity reveals that all classes exhibit relatively simple forms, with a slight increase in the complexity of urban fragments between 1985 and 2024. This relative stability contrasts with observations of Mouléry et al. (2024), who document more pronounced fragmentation in Mediterranean contexts. Finally, diversity indices reveal a slight decrease in overall diversity, but with a better distribution of classes, suggesting a more homogeneous landscape structure, possibly due to the persistence of agricultural areas. As highlighted Bober et al. (2016), this evolution towards controlled heterogeneity is characteristic of periurban landscapes in transition, where natural and anthropogenic dynamics gradually balance each other.

D. Future prediction of the ZUK urban landscape

The model's learning curve value illustrates efficient model convergence, signifying successful adaptation to the training data. Simultaneously, cross-validation of the Kappa index indicates that the model possesses excellent generalization capabilities beyond the training set. This aligns with the recommendations of (Olson et al. 2016) for rigorously evaluating the performance of predictive models. Kappa index of 0.99 reinforces this finding, demonstrating very high accuracy in prediction, a characteristic sometimes observed in models calibrated with highly homogeneous or optimized datasets (Kuhn et al. 2019). These results place this model among the top performers for the task under

consideration, while also indicating its reliable operational use for the intended applications. Other authors emphasize the importance of combining several indicators (validation error, Kappa score, ROC curves) to avoid overfitting and ensure robustness (Gootjes-Dreesbach et al. 2020). Furthermore, a detailed analysis of these curves is essential to detect the phases where the model begins to overfit or underfit, which was not observed in this study, demonstrating the quality of the learning protocol used.

Regarding the transition model, three (3) major changes are observed and the most significant change is the conversion of FL and CF to A. This transition extends from the urban center to peri-urban areas, illustrating a dynamic of progressive spatial urbanization. This observation aligns with the work of Oladokoun et al. (2024), who highlight a marked trend of urban expansion at the expense of natural and agricultural land in Togolese cities (Atakpamé and Kara), with a direct impact on landscape fragmentation and the lasting modification of land use. In addition, the study by Traore et al. (2021) highlights that this accelerated transition between classes FL and A reflects the increasing socio-economic pressures linked to rapid urbanization, particularly around major urban centers. They also emphasize the need to better integrate these dynamics into land-use planning policies in order to limit deforestation and the loss of agricultural land, while simultaneously meeting the needs of urban growth.

By 2050, land use in the ZUK is expected to undergo profound transformation, marked by rapid urbanization and a reconfiguration of agricultural and natural spaces. A are projected to expand significantly, consolidating their dominance over the territory. This trend aligns with recent observations by Oladokoun et al. (2024), who document accelerated urban growth in West Africa, often at the expense of natural spaces. Tossoukpe et al. (2025), in their study of urbanization in Lomé (Togo) and Accra (Ghana), confirm that this expansion is particularly pronounced in periurban areas, where the demand for housing and infrastructure is placing increasing pressure on available land.

Conversely, CF is expected to decline substantially, illustrating the progressive conversion of these lands into urbanized areas. This phenomenon, also observed by Enomah (2022) in Central Africa and (Tay 2025) in Indonesia, reflects a growing tension between urban development and the maintenance of agricultural activities. Andrews Korah Norman (2024) and Radoine et al. (2024) emphasize that this dynamic is typical of developing cities, where urbanization is often accompanied by a loss of arable land and landscape fragmentation. Despite this pressure, FL could experience a slight increase, suggesting local conservation or reforestation efforts. On the other hand, BS is expected to decrease significantly, indicating a reduction in degraded or unexploited areas. This trend corroborates the findings of Onaolapo (2020), which highlight the link between

urbanization, the reduction of bare soil, and the loss of forest land. This evolution may also reflect an improvement in land management practices, particularly through ecological restoration programs or sustainable agricultural intensification.

Overall, this projection reveals intense urbanization, exerting increasing pressure on agricultural land and bare soils, while suggesting the partial preservation of forest areas. These dynamics highlight the major challenges Kpalimé urban zone will face in reconciling urban growth, the preservation of agricultural land, and the sustainable management of natural resources. Cassatella et al. (2025) emphasize the need for developing countries to adopt integrated planning strategies, combining urban planning, ecosystem protection, and support for periurban agriculture.

V. CONCLUSIONS

A diachronic analysis of urbanization in Kpalimé over nearly four decades (1985-2024) highlights rapid urban dynamics, marked by a considerable expansion of agglomerations, increasing from 429.07 ha in 1985 to 1624.26 ha in 2024. This growth, particularly intense between 2000 and 2015, illustrates a phase of uncontrolled urban sprawl that has profoundly reshaped the morphology of the local landscape. Results from remote sensing indices (NDVI, NDBI and BU) and landscape metrics reveal an initial fragmentation of the urban fabric, followed by a more recent process of recomposition and densification, reflecting a progressive trend towards the consolidation of Agglomerations.

At the same time, the dynamics of agricultural and forest land reveal a high vulnerability to human pressures. Crops and fallow land, after a prolonged decline between 1985 and 2000 (-371.08 ha), have recently recovered (528.28 ha between 2015 and 2024), reaching 1502.65 ha in 2024. Conversely, forest land, initially increasing between 1985 and 2000 (150.87 ha), has experienced a sharp decline (-62.98 ha between 2000 and 2015, then -18.47 ha between 2015 and 2024), reflecting the impact of urban and agricultural pressures. These changes reflect increased competition between urbanization, agriculture, and ecosystem conservation.

Modeling using Markov chains confirms the trend towards urban expansion by 2050, with a projected increase in built-up areas to 2,119.02 hectares (57.58% of the territory), intensifying pressure on natural resources and the risks of deforestation and loss of crops/fallows. These results, by providing a robust methodological framework, call for more proactive and integrated territorial governance. The implementation of sustainable urban planning strategies, based on a link between growth and sustainable development, is crucial. Economic development, social inclusion and ecological preservation appear as an essential condition to ensure the socio-ecological resilience of the city of Kpalimé

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in the face of future demographic and environmental challenges.

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